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7 **A new approach to the central gravitational field in vacuum space**
8 **Implementation of General Relativity in finite space to the MOND theory**

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13 **Abstract:** this document presents a new approach to the central symmetric gravitational field in vacuum space. Two
14 arbitrary functions are needed in this approach. In general, these functions do not induce any difference between this
15 metric and the classical Schwarzschild metric, as it is claimed by the Birkhoff theorem. However, we managed to get round
16 the Birkhoff theorem by choosing a triangular signal for the needed arbitrary functions; in this case, the metric is broken
17 down into four distinct metrics which replace each other cyclically over time, due to the incessant permutation of the
18 spatial/temporal role between the r and t coordinates. The average metric, obtained from the four distinct metrics, is
19 different from the classical Schwarzschild metric. In this new metric, the Riemann space-time curvature is bounded and
20 oscillatory; the orbital velocity of a massive particle does not vary with respect to the radial distance, which allows finding
21 the result obtained in the asymptotic area of the MOND theory by Mordehai Milgrom. Then, it appears that this metric can
22 apply in an area which is governed by the Tully-Fisher law, without any dark matter in this area. By combining this
23 oscillatory metric and the classical Schwarzschild metric, we obtain in the framework of General Relativity a velocity
24 profile of the stars of a galaxy similar to the profile described in MOND, without any dark matter.
25

26 **Résumé:** Ce document présente une nouvelle approche du champ de gravitation central dans le vide. Cette approche
27 nécessite l'introduction de deux fonctions arbitraires. En général, ces fonctions n'induisent aucune différence entre cette
28 métrique et la métrique classique de Schwarzschild, comme l'affirme le théorème de Birkhoff. Cependant, nous avons pu
29 contourner le théorème de Birkhoff en choisissant pour les fonctions requises un signal triangulaire ; dans ce cas, la
30 métrique est éclatée en quatre métrique distinctes qui se succèdent cycliquement au cours du temps, à cause de la
31 permutation incessante du rôle spatial/temporel des coordonnées r et t . La métrique moyenne, obtenue à partir des
32 quatre métriques distinctes, est différente de la métrique classique de Schwarzschild. Dans cette nouvelle métrique, la
33 courbure Riemannienne de l'espace-temps est bornée et oscillatoire ; la vitesse orbitale d'une particule massive ne varie
34 pas en fonction de la distance radiale, ce qui permet de retrouver le résultat obtenu dans la zone asymptotique de la
35 théorie MOND de Mordehai Milgrom. Ainsi, il apparait que cette métrique peut s'appliquer dans une zone qui est
36 gouvernée par la loi de Tully-Fisher, sans aucune matière noire dans cette zone. En combinant cette métrique oscillatoire
37 et la métrique classique de Schwarzschild, nous obtenons dans le cadre de la Relativité Générale un profil de vitesse des
38 étoiles d'une galaxie similaire au profil décrit dans MOND, sans aucune matière noire.
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40 Key words: metric; non static; galaxy; Schwarzschild; Tully-Fisher; MOND; curvature; bounded; oscillatory; dark matter;
41 Birkhoff

1 Introduction

We know, from the publication of the Schwarzschild metric (1916) and the Birkhoff's theorem (1923) that a central symmetric gravitational field in infinite vacuum space is automatically static in the framework of General Relativity. In spherical coordinates (R, θ, φ) , the Schwarzschild metric is defined by the space-time interval ds:

$$ds^2 = (1 - R_0/R)dt^2 - dR^2/(1 - R_0/R) - R^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2) \quad (1.1)$$

where t is the time coordinate in meters ($t = c \times t_s$ where t_s is the time coordinate in sec), c is the light speed, R is the radial space coordinate, θ is the colatitude, φ is the longitude, G is the gravitational constant, M is the mass of the central massive body, and $R_0 = 2 GM/c^2$.

We will present in this document a variant of the Schwarzschild metric, defined in finite space. This variant needs two arbitrary functions. Most of these functions do not induce any difference with respect to the classical Schwarzschild metric. However, we will see that at least one particular case using a periodic function does exist, presenting a different behavior with respect to the Schwarzschild metric. In this particular case, trajectories of peripheral stars in a galaxy are modified. These trajectories are in agreement with the Tully-Fisher law as it is modeled in the asymptotic area of the MOND theory [1, 2, 3] by Mordehai Milgrom.

In the mathematical expressions of this document, the t, r exponents represent the partial derivatives with respect to the t, r coordinates; the u, v exponents represent the full derivatives with respect to the u, v functions.

2 Transformation of the space-time interval

Using the transformation:
$$dr = dR/|1 - R_0/R| \quad (2.1)$$

we transform the ds interval (1.1) in the following form, in tortoise coordinates (r, θ, φ) :

$$ds^2 = [1 - R_0/R(r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - [R(r)]^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2) \quad (2.2)$$

$$r = R + R_0 \text{Log} |(R/R_0) - 1| \quad (2.3)$$

The ds interval (2.2) can be rewritten in the equivalent form:

$$ds^2 = e^{2v(r)}dt^2 - e^{2v(r)}dr^2 - [R(r)]^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2) \quad (2.4)$$

where $v(r), R(r)$ are the functions defined by the relations (2.2) and (2.3). We postulate that this metric can be extended in the form of a non static metric in finite space, making the hypothesis that the $v(r), R(r)$ functions can be extended in the temporal domain with the form $v(t,r), R(t,r)$, these functions being defined as the solutions of the tensor equation: $\mathbf{R}_{ij} = 0$, where \mathbf{R}_{ij} is the Ricci tensor. By hypothesis, we define the non static metric by the relation:

$$ds^2 = e^{2v(t,r)}dt^2 - e^{2v(t,r)}dr^2 - [R(t,r)]^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2) \quad (2.5)$$

3 Summary of the non static metric in finite space

The complete demonstration is reported in Appendix A.

Let us set two arbitrary radial coordinates: r_B and r_M ($r_B < r_M$), and two arbitrary two times differentiable functions: $HP(u)$ and $HM(v)$. In finite space, the solution of the tensor equation: $\mathbf{R}_{ij} = 0$ is defined by the following relations:

$$r_B \leq r \leq r_M \quad (3.1)$$

$$z = R(t,r) + R_0 \text{Log} |(R(t,r)/R_0) - 1| \quad (3.2)$$

$$u = t + r ; v = t - r \quad (3.3)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial r^2} = 0 \Rightarrow z = HP(u) - HM(v) \quad (3.4)$$

$$e^{2v(t,r)} = 4HP^u HM^v [1 - R_0/R(t,r)] \quad (3.5)$$

$$ds^2 = 4 HP^u HM^v [1 - R_0/R(t,r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - [R(t,r)]^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2) \quad (3.6)$$

83 The $R(t,r)$ function is implicitly defined by the relations (3.2) and (3.4). The following mathematical
 84 transformations show that it seems possible, a priori, to transform in all cases the metric (3.6) in the classical
 85 Schwarzschild metric. These transformations are made obviously with the assumption that they are all justified.

$$86 \quad ds^2 = 4 HP^u HM^v [1 - R_0/R(t,r)] du dv - [R(t,r)]^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2) \quad (3.7)$$

$$87 \quad ds^2 = 4 [1 - R_0/R(t,r)] dHP dHM - \{R[HP(u) - HM(v)]\}^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2) \quad (3.8)$$

$$88 \quad ds^2 = (1 - R_0/R) [(dHP + dHM)^2 - (dHP - dHM)^2] - [R(HP(u) - HM(v))]^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2) \quad (3.9)$$

$$89 \quad z = HP(u) - HM(v) = R + R_0 \text{Log} |(R/R_0) - 1| \quad (3.10)$$

90 Let us rename: $HP(u)+HM(v) = t'$; $HP(u)-HM(v) = r'$, we obtain:

$$91 \quad ds^2 = [1 - R_0/R(r')] [(dt')^2 - (dr')^2] - [R(r')]^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2) \quad (3.11)$$

$$92 \quad z = r' = R + R_0 \text{Log} |(R/R_0) - 1| \quad (3.12)$$

93 The relations (3.11) and (3.12) define the classical Schwarzschild metric written in tortoise coordinates. The
 94 metric (3.6) can be deduced directly from the static metric by performing inversely the operations (3.7) to (3.12).
 95 However, in this case, the $HP(u)$ and $HM(v)$ functions are artificially introduced without any justification, as in the
 96 complete demonstration (cf. Appendix A), these functions are introduced as the solutions of a transport equation (cf.
 97 relations (A2.7) and (A2.8)); more, in the inverse calculation process, we do not prove that the metric (3.6) is the only
 98 solution of the tensor equation $\mathbf{R}_{ij} = 0$ obtained from the metric (2.5).

99 Finally, for some kinds of $HP(u)$ and $HM(v)$ functions, the t, r coordinates permute continuously over time their
 100 temporal/spatial role, which can make impossible the coordinate's transformations allowing to find the classical
 101 Schwarzschild metric.

102 Let us set a finite space. We have to define the $HP(u)$ and $HM(v)$ functions. Let us suppose that the $R(t,r)$ function
 103 has physically an upper bound, as : $R(t,r) \leq R_c$, where R_c is a physical function depending only on the mass of the central
 104 massive body. It is clear that the classical Schwarzschild metric could not take into account this physical constraint. We
 105 will show in §5 that it is possible by using the metric (3.6).

107 4 First integrals of the geodesics in the general case of the non static metric

108 Let us set : $\kappa = 1$ for the massive particles, and $\kappa = 0$ for the particles without mass; E_r : the energy of the particle;
 109 h : the angular momentum of the particle; σ : the proper time of the particle in meters ($\sigma = c\tau$ where τ is the proper time in
 110 seconds) for a massive particle, or an affine parameter for a particle without mass, and let us set: $w = 1/R$.

111 The first integrals can be deduced easily from the first integrals of the Schwarzschild metric; however, their direct
 112 calculation has been reported in Appendix B. These first integrals are defined by the following relations, where R, w, r, t
 113 are the coordinates of a massive or without mass particle, according to the κ value:

$$114 \quad \theta = \pi/2 \quad (4.1)$$

$$115 \quad R^2 \frac{d\varphi}{d\sigma} = h \quad (4.2)$$

$$116 \quad \left(\frac{dR}{d\sigma}\right)^2 + (1 - R_0/R) [(h^2/R^2) + \kappa] = (E_r)^2 \quad (4.3)$$

$$117 \quad \frac{d^2w}{d\varphi^2} + w - 3w^2 R_0/2 = \kappa R_0/(2h^2) \quad (4.4)$$

$$118 \quad \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)(HM^v + HP^u) + (dR/d\varphi)(HM^v - HP^u)}{4HP^u HM^v (1 - R_0/R)} \quad (4.5)$$

$$119 \quad \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)(HM^v - HP^u) + (dR/d\varphi)(HM^v + HP^u)}{4HP^u HM^v (1 - R_0/R)} \quad (4.6)$$

120 Let us set V_T the orbital velocity of a massive particle moving along a circular orbit defined by : $R = R_s$; we obtain:

$$121 \quad (E_r)^2 = \frac{[1 - R_0/R_s]^2}{[1 - (3/2)R_0/R_s]} \quad (4.7)$$

$$\frac{(R_s)^2 E_r/h}{(1-R_0/R_s)} = \frac{R_s \sqrt{R_s}}{\sqrt{G M/c^2}} \quad (4.8)$$

$$\frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R_s)^2 E_r/h}{(1-R_0/R_s)} \frac{(HM^v + HP^u)}{4HP^u HM^v} = \frac{R_s \sqrt{R_s}}{\sqrt{G M/c^2}} \frac{(HM^v + HP^u)}{4HP^u HM^v} \quad (4.9)$$

$$(V_T)^2 = (R_s)^2 \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dT}\right)^2 = (R_s)^2 \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dt}\right)^2 \left(\frac{dt}{dT}\right)^2 = \frac{G M/R_s}{(1-R_0/R_s)} \frac{4HP^u HM^v}{(HM^v + HP^u)^2} \quad (4.10)$$

The detailed calculations of these formulae are reported in Appendix B (§2 and §3). The relations (4.1) to (4.4) are identical to the corresponding relations of the classical Schwarzschild metric. Differences appear only when we calculate the t, r coordinates, and the real values of time and distances. For calculating the geodesics, we have to proceed in the following manner: 1/ calculation of the $w(\varphi)$ function deduced from the relation (4.4), then $R(\varphi) = 1/w(\varphi)$; 2/ calculation of the $HP(u)$ and $HM(v)$ functions; 3/ calculation of the t, r coordinates from the relations (4.5) and (4.6); 4/ calculation of the real values of time and distance.

The deviation δ_R of the light rays is obtained with the classical formula:

$$\delta_R = 4GM/[c^2 R(t, r)] \quad (4.11)$$

The Kretschmann scalar $Kr = R^{abcd} R_{abcd}$, calculated from the Riemann tensor R is obtained as:

$$Kr = 48 (G^2 M^2)/[c^4 R(t, r)^6] \quad (4.12)$$

5 Metric with a bounded z function

Define a spherical finite space by: $r_B \leq r \leq r_M$, where r_B and r_M are two arbitrary radial coordinates. Define the triangular signal $F_{tr}^\omega(x)$ with pulsation ω and amplitude equal to $\frac{\pi}{2\omega}$. Let us set two arbitrary positive numbers ω and R_C :

$$F_{tr}^\omega(x) = -\frac{4}{\pi\omega} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\cos(2k+1)\omega x}{(2k+1)^2} \quad (5.1)$$

Its derivative is the square signal $F_{sq}^\omega(x)$ with amplitude equal to 1:

$$\frac{d F_{tr}^\omega(x)}{dx} = F_{sq}^\omega(x) = \frac{4}{\pi} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\sin(2k+1)\omega x}{(2k+1)} \quad (5.2)$$

$$\text{Let us set: } HP(u) = R_C + F_{tr}^\omega(u)/2 ; HM(v) = F_{tr}^\omega(v)/2 \quad (5.3)$$

$$HP^u = F_{sq}^\omega(u)/2 ; HM^v = F_{sq}^\omega(v)/2 \quad (5.4)$$

$$z = HP(u) - HM(v) = R_C + [F_{tr}^\omega(u) - F_{tr}^\omega(v)]/2 = R + R_0 \text{Log} |(R/R_0) - 1| \quad (5.5)$$

$$dz = du HP^u - dv HM^v = du F_{sq}^\omega(u)/2 - dv F_{sq}^\omega(v)/2 = dR/(1 - R_0/R) \quad (5.6)$$

$R(t, r)$ depends only on cosine functions in $t+r$ and $t-r$, then $R(r, t) = R(t, r)$. The metric (3.6) becomes:

$$ds^2 = F_{sq}^\omega(t+r) F_{sq}^\omega(t-r) [1 - R_0/R(t, r)] (dt^2 - dr^2) - [R(t, r)]^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2) \quad (5.7)$$

Analysis of the impact of the changes of sign of the derivatives HP^u and HM^v on the metric:

$$\text{Let us set: } \Omega^2 = [R(t, r)]^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2).$$

$$1^{\text{st}} \text{ mode: } F_{sq}^\omega(t+r) = 1 \text{ and } F_{sq}^\omega(t-r) = 1 \Rightarrow HP^u = \frac{1}{2}; HM^v = \frac{1}{2} \Rightarrow ds^2 = [1 - R_0/R(t, r)] [dt^2 - dr^2] - \Omega^2$$

$$dz = du F_{sq}^\omega(u)/2 - dv F_{sq}^\omega(v)/2 = (du - dv)/2 = dr$$

$$\text{Geodesic from relations (4.5) and (4.6) : } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1-R_0/R)} ; \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(1-R_0/R)} \quad (\text{dt is temporal; dr is spatial})$$

$$2^{\text{nd}} \text{ mode: } F_{sq}^\omega(t+r) = 1 \text{ and } F_{sq}^\omega(t-r) = -1 \Rightarrow HP^u = \frac{1}{2}; HM^v = -\frac{1}{2} \Rightarrow ds^2 = [1 - R_0/R(t, r)] [dr^2 - dt^2] - \Omega^2$$

The differential dr becomes temporal, the differential dt becomes spatial.

$$dz = du F_{sq}^\omega(u)/2 - dv F_{sq}^\omega(v)/2 = (du + dv)/2 = dt$$

$$\text{Geodesic: } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(1-R_0/R)} ; \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1-R_0/R)} \quad (\text{dt is spatial; dr is temporal})$$

$$3^{\text{rd}} \text{ mode: } F_{sq}^\omega(t+r) = -1 \text{ and } F_{sq}^\omega(t-r) = 1 \Rightarrow HP^u = -\frac{1}{2}; HM^v = \frac{1}{2} \Rightarrow ds^2 = [1 - R_0/R(t, r)] [dr^2 - dt^2] - \Omega^2$$

The differential dr becomes temporal, the differential dt becomes spatial.

$$dz = du F_{sq}^\omega(u)/2 - dv F_{sq}^\omega(v)/2 = (-du - dv)/2 = -dt$$

$$\text{Geodesic: } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = -\frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(1-R_0/R)} ; \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = -\frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1-R_0/R)} \quad (\text{dt is spatial; dr is temporal})$$

$$4^{\text{th}} \text{ mode: } F_{sq}^\omega(t+r) = -1 \text{ and } F_{sq}^\omega(t-r) = -1 \Rightarrow \text{HP}^u = -\frac{1}{2} ; \text{HM}^v = -\frac{1}{2} \Rightarrow ds^2 = [1 - R_0/R(t,r)][dt^2 - dr^2] - \Omega^2$$

$$dz = du F_{sq}^\omega(u)/2 - dv F_{sq}^\omega(v)/2 = (-du + dv)/2 = -dr$$

$$\text{Geodesic: } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = -\frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1-R_0/R)} ; \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = -\frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(1-R_0/R)} \quad (\text{dt is temporal; dr is spatial})$$

The temporal differentials of the coordinates have to be aligned on the real time, as we have to take into account the first integral: $R^2 \frac{d\varphi}{d\sigma} = h \Rightarrow$ variation of the φ angle with respect to the proper time is monotonic. Then, we have to change the sign of the temporal differentials in the 3rd and 4th modes for aligning them on the 1st mode that we set as the reference mode. By homogenizing the coordinate's symbols for obtaining in all modes dt as the temporal differential and dr as the spatial differential, we rewrite:

$$1^{\text{st}} \text{ mode : } dz = dr ; \text{ geodesic: } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1-R_0/R)} ; \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(1-R_0/R)} \quad (5.8)$$

$$2^{\text{nd}} \text{ mode : } dz = dr ; \text{ geodesic: } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1-R_0/R)} ; \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(1-R_0/R)} \quad (5.9)$$

$$3^{\text{st}} \text{ mode : } dz = -dr ; \text{ geodesic : } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1-R_0/R)} ; \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = -\frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(1-R_0/R)} \quad (5.10)$$

$$4^{\text{th}} \text{ mode : } dz = -dr ; \text{ geodesic : } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1-R_0/R)} ; \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = -\frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(1-R_0/R)} \quad (5.11)$$

$$\text{In all modes : } ds^2 = [1 - R_0/R(t,r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - [R(t,r)]^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2) \quad (5.12)$$

The R function value is constant over time, but the derivative $z^r = R^r/(1 - R_0/R) = \pm 1$ oscillates continuously over time. The real time differential interval dT between two events located at (r, θ, φ) is:

$$c dT = \sqrt{1 - R_0/R(t,r)} dt \approx dt \quad (\text{case: } R_0/R(t,r) \ll 1) \quad (5.13)$$

The real radial distance differential interval dL_r is:

$$dL_r = \sqrt{1 - R_0/R(t,r)} dr \approx dr \quad (\text{case: } R_0/R(t,r) \ll 1) \quad (5.14)$$

$$\text{We obtain, with } \varepsilon = \pm 1 : \quad dz = \varepsilon dr = dR/(1 - R_0/R) \quad (5.15)$$

The metric formula (5.12) is similar to that of the classical Schwarzschild metric written in tortoise coordinates, but in the formula (5.12) R is a function of time (although the value of the R function remains constant over time). If we used the transformation: $dr^2 = dR^2/(1 - R_0/R)^2$, the metric (5.12) could be transformed as:

$$ds^2 = [1 - R_0/R]dt^2 - dR^2/[1 - R_0/R] - R^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2) \quad (5.16)$$

The formula (5.16) is formally identical to the formula of the classical Schwarzschild metric; however, this formula is not justified, as, from the relations (5.15) the function r(R) does not exist. This result proves that a non static metric (3.6) cannot be transformed in all cases in the classical Schwarzschild metric.

6 Geodesics of the metric with a bounded z function

From the relations (5.8) to (5.12) we obtain:

$$\frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1-R_0/R)} \Rightarrow \frac{dT}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{c \sqrt{1-R_0/R}} \quad (6.1)$$

$$\frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \varepsilon \frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(1-R_0/R)} \quad (\varepsilon = \pm 1) \quad (6.2)$$

Let us set the case of a massive particle whose trajectory is defined as $R(\varphi) = R_s = \text{constant} \Rightarrow (dR/d\varphi) = 0$. Let us set V_r the radial velocity, and V_T the orbital velocity. We obtain the following results:

$$\frac{dr}{d\varphi} = 0 \quad (6.3)$$

$$(V_r/c) = 0 \quad (6.4)$$

$$\text{from relation (4.10) : } (V_T)^2 = (R_s)^2 \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dT} \right)^2 = \frac{(G M / R_s)}{(1-R_0/R_s)} \quad (6.5)$$

$$\frac{(V_T)^2}{R_s} = \frac{[G M / (R_s)^2]}{(1-R_0/R_s)} = A_0$$

If $R_0/R_s \ll 1$:

$$(V_T)^2 \approx (G M / R_s) \quad (6.6)$$

$$(V_T)^2/R_s \approx [G M / (R_s)^2] \approx A_0 \Rightarrow R_s \approx \sqrt{G M / A_0}$$

$$(V_T)^4 \approx G M A_0 \quad (6.7)$$

A_0 is the value of the radial acceleration. We obtain for the orbital velocity (6.6) the classical Newton formula, provided that we replace in the formula the distance parameter by the local value of the R function. The R function value being constant in this finite space, the orbital velocity of the stars located in this area is constant. This result is in agreement with the asymptotic tendency of the MOND theory [1, 2, 3]. In this theory, the asymptotic orbital velocity V_{outM} of stars in a galaxy is defined by the relation: $(V_{\text{outM}})^4 = G M_b a_0$, where $a_0 \sim 1.2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m.s}^{-2}$ and where M_b is equal to the baryonic mass of the galaxy. By identifying the orbital velocity V_T and the velocity V_{outM} , and setting $M = M_b$, we obtain:

$$(V_{\text{outM}})^4 = (V_T)^4 = G M_b a_0 = G M_b A_0 \Rightarrow A_0 = a_0 \quad (6.8)$$

$$\frac{(V_T)^2}{R_c} \approx \frac{G M}{(R_c)^2} = a_0 \quad (6.9)$$

We conclude that, in the asymptotic area of the MOND theory, the orbital velocity of the stars is in agreement with a particular solution of the non static Schwarzschild metric in finite space. In this area, the constant values of the deviation of light δ_R and the Kretschmann scalar Kr are obtained by the relations:

$$\delta_R = 4\sqrt{G M_b a_0}/c^2 \quad (6.10)$$

$$\text{Kr} = 48 (a_0)^3 / (c^4 G M_b) \quad (6.11)$$

$$\text{Let us set: } Ckr = 48 (a_0)^3 / (c^4 G) \sim 1.5 \times 10^{-52} \text{ Kg.m}^{-4} \quad (6.12)$$

$$\text{Kr} = Ckr/M_b \quad (6.13)$$

If we make the assumption that the relation $(V_{\text{outM}})^4 = G M_b a_0$ is a true physical law, we deduce that in a galaxy, the radial asymptotic value a_0 of the acceleration a_r is a universal constant such as: $a_r \geq a_0$. According to the relation (6.13), the Kretschmann scalar has a lower bound, inversely proportional to the baryonic mass; it follows that the Riemann space-time curvature has a lower bound in a galaxy. Consequently, for obtaining a metric with a bounded z function physically significant (i.e. in agreement with the Tully-Fisher law), we have to set: $\frac{[G M / (R_c)^2]}{(1-R_0/R_c)} = a_0 \Rightarrow$

$$R_c = \sqrt{(R_0/2)^2 + G M/a_0} + R_0/2 \approx \sqrt{G M/a_0}.$$

7 Overview of the MOND theory

In its MOND theory, Mordehai Milgrom (Milgrom 1983 [1]), makes the hypothesis that the Newton gravitational acceleration a_N , obtained by the formula: $a_N = GM/r^2$ changes its form for a particular value of the acceleration, the critical value: $a_0 \sim 1.2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m.s}^{-2}$; the relation $a_r = a_N$ becomes: $a_r = a_N \times \mu(a_r/a_0)$, where $\mu(a_r/a_0)$ is an empirical interpolation function, equal to 1 if $a_r \gg a_0$, and equal to: $\mu = a_r/a_0$ si $a_r \ll a_0$ in the acceleration low regime. The limit value of the acceleration a_r is: $a_r = \sqrt{a_N \times a_0} = \sqrt{G M_b a_0}/r$. The acceleration classical formula in $1/r^2$ is replaced by a formula in $1/r$. A currently used $\mu(a_r/a_0)$ function is defined by the expression:

$$\mu(a_r/a_0) = (a_r/a_0) / \sqrt{1 + (a_r/a_0)^2} \quad (7.1)$$

Consequently, the asymptotic velocity V_{outM} of the peripheral stars in a galaxy is obtained by the following formula: $V_{\text{outM}}^2/r = \sqrt{G M_b a_0}/r \Rightarrow V_{\text{outM}}^4 = G M_b a_0$. MOND is in agreement with the Tully-Fisher empirical law, in which the

baryonic mass of a galaxy is proportional to V_{outM}^4 (Moffat 2005 [2]). Milgrom has calculated the a_0 value for being in agreement with the measured stars velocities.

For approximating the location of the MOND transition area in a galaxy, let us set: $L_A = k_A R_C$ and $L_B = k_B R_C$. We make the assumption that the transition area begins at the distance L_A and ends at the distance L_B . By using the formula (7.1), we have obtained the approximate values: $k_A \approx 0.4$ and $k_B \approx 2.5 \Rightarrow k_A k_B = 1$. Using the interpolation formula (7.1), we obtain the following results:

$$k_A = 0.4 \Rightarrow \text{interpolated acceleration/ Newton acceleration} = 1.01$$

$$k_B = 2.5 \Rightarrow \text{interpolated acceleration/ MOND asymptotic acceleration} = 1.04$$

The MOND theory has obtained quite good results in describing the profile velocity in a lot of galaxies. The results obtained at §6 (cf. relation (6.8)) show that we can model the MOND asymptotic area by a non static metric with a bounded z function. Then, the asymptotic MOND behavior can be explained by General Relativity without any dark matter.

However, we observe an important difference between the MOND theory and our solution, concerning the concept of acceleration. In the MOND theory, in the asymptotic area, the radial acceleration is: $a_r = a_f = \sqrt{GM_b a_0}/r = V^2/r$. This expression is quite different from our expression: $a_r \approx GM_b/R^2 \approx V^2/R \approx a_0$. In our solution, the acceleration does not vary in the asymptotic area: the Milgrom constant a_0 is the lowest value of the radial acceleration, as in the MOND theory, the acceleration is varying in $1/r$ in this area. This result could have important consequences for generalizing our solution to clusters of galaxies.

8 Hybrid metric

This hybrid metric is a combination of the classical Schwarzschild metric and of the metric with a z bounded function. We are using it for modeling the transition MOND area. We define a finite spherical space by : $r_A \leq r \leq r_B$, where r_A and r_B are two arbitrary radial coordinates. Let us set two arbitrary positive numbers α and ω , and the functions $HP(u)$ and $HM(v)$:

$$HP(u) = r_A + \alpha u/2 + F_{\text{tr}}^\omega(u)/2 ; \quad HM(v) = \alpha v/2 + F_{\text{tr}}^\omega(v)/2 \quad (8.1)$$

$$HP^u = [\alpha + F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(u)]/2 ; \quad HM^v = [\alpha + F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(v)]/2 \quad (8.2)$$

$$z = HP(u) - HM(v) = r_A + \alpha (u - v)/2 + [F_{\text{tr}}^\omega(u) - F_{\text{tr}}^\omega(v)]/2 = R + R_0 \text{Log} |(R/R_0) - 1| \quad (8.3)$$

$$dz = du HP^u - dv HM^v = du [\alpha + F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(u)]/2 - dv [\alpha + F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(v)]/2 = dR/(1 - R_0/R) \quad (8.4)$$

The metric (3.6) becomes:

$$ds^2 = [\alpha + F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(u)] [\alpha + F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(v)] (1 - R_0/R)(dt^2 - dr^2) - [R(t, r)]^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2) \quad (8.5)$$

$$\text{Let us set : } \Omega^2 = [R(t, r)]^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2) .$$

$$\text{Geodesic from relations (4.5), (4.6) : } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)(HM^v + HP^u) + (dR/d\varphi)(HM^v - HP^u)}{4HP^u HM^v (1 - R_0/R)} ; \quad \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)(HM^v - HP^u) + (dR/d\varphi)(HM^v + HP^u)}{4HP^u HM^v (1 - R_0/R)}$$

Analysis of the impact of the changes of sign of the derivatives HP^u and HM^v on the metric:

$$1^{\text{st}} \text{ mode : } F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(t + r) = 1 \text{ and } F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(t - r) = 1 \Rightarrow HP^u = (\alpha + 1)/2 ; HM^v = (\alpha + 1)/2$$

$$ds^2 = (\alpha + 1)^2 [1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$$

$$dz = du (\alpha + 1)/2 - dv (\alpha + 1)/2 = \alpha dr + dr$$

$$\text{Geodesic: } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(\alpha + 1)(1 - R_0/R)} ; \quad \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(\alpha + 1)(1 - R_0/R)}$$

$$2^{\text{nd}} \text{ mode : } F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(t + r) = 1 \text{ and } F_{\text{sq}}^\omega(t - r) = -1 \Rightarrow HP^u = (\alpha + 1)/2 ; HM^v = (\alpha - 1)/2$$

$$ds^2 = (\alpha^2 - 1) [1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$$

$$dz = du (\alpha + 1)/2 - dv (\alpha - 1)/2 = \alpha dr + dt$$

$$\text{Geodesic: } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)\alpha - (dR/d\varphi)}{(\alpha^2 - 1)(1 - R_0/R)} ; \quad \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{-(R^2 E_r/h) + (dR/d\varphi)\alpha}{(\alpha^2 - 1)(1 - R_0/R)}$$

3rdmode : $F_{sq}^\omega(t+r) = -1$ and $F_{sq}^\omega(t-r) = 1 \Rightarrow HP^u = (\alpha - 1)/2$; $HM^v = (\alpha + 1)/2$

$$ds^2 = (\alpha^2 - 1) [1 - R_0/R(r,t)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$$

$$dz = du (\alpha - 1)/2 - dv (\alpha + 1)/2 = \alpha dr - dt$$

$$\text{Geodesic: } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)\alpha + (dR/d\varphi)}{(\alpha^2 - 1)(1 - R_0/R)} ; \quad \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h) + (dR/d\varphi)\alpha}{(\alpha^2 - 1)(1 - R_0/R)}$$

4thmode : $F_{sq}^\omega(t+r) = -1$ and $F_{sq}^\omega(t-r) = -1 \Rightarrow HP^u = (\alpha - 1)/2$; $HM^v = (\alpha - 1)/2$

$$ds^2 = (\alpha - 1)^2 [1 - R_0/R(t,r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2$$

$$dz = du (\alpha - 1)/2 - dv (\alpha - 1)/2 = \alpha dr - dr$$

$$\text{Geodesic: } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(\alpha - 1)(1 - R_0/R)} ; \quad \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(\alpha - 1)(1 - R_0/R)}$$

Summary:

$$1^{\text{st}}\text{mode} : dz = \alpha dr + dr ; \text{ geodesic: } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(\alpha + 1)(1 - R_0/R)} ; \quad \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(\alpha + 1)(1 - R_0/R)} \quad (8.6)$$

$$2^{\text{nd}}\text{mode} : dz = \alpha dr + dt ; \text{ geodesic: } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)\alpha - (dR/d\varphi)}{(\alpha^2 - 1)(1 - R_0/R)} ; \quad \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{-(R^2 E_r/h) + (dR/d\varphi)\alpha}{(\alpha^2 - 1)(1 - R_0/R)} \quad (8.7)$$

$$3^{\text{rd}}\text{mode} : dz = \alpha dr - dt ; \text{ geodesic: } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)\alpha + (dR/d\varphi)}{(\alpha^2 - 1)(1 - R_0/R)} ; \quad \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h) + (dR/d\varphi)\alpha}{(\alpha^2 - 1)(1 - R_0/R)} \quad (8.8)$$

$$4^{\text{th}}\text{mode} : dz = \alpha dr - dr ; \text{ geodesic: } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(\alpha - 1)(1 - R_0/R)} ; \quad \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(\alpha - 1)(1 - R_0/R)} \quad (8.9)$$

We can obtain two kinds of solution, depending on whether $\alpha > 1$ or $\alpha < 1$.

A/First case: $\alpha > 1$

For the circular geodesics of a massive particle, we set: $dr = 0$

$$1^{\text{st}}\text{mode} : dz = \alpha dr + dr ; \text{ circular geodesics : } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(\alpha + 1)(1 - R_0/R)} ; \quad \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = 0 \Rightarrow dR = 0$$

$$2^{\text{nd}}\text{mode: } dz = \alpha dr + dt ; \text{ circular geodesics : } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{\alpha(1 - R_0/R)} = \frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(1 - R_0/R)} ; \quad \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = 0 \Rightarrow (R^2 E_r/h) - (dR/d\varphi)\alpha = 0$$

$$3^{\text{rd}}\text{mode} : dz = \alpha dr - dt ; \text{ circular geodesics : } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{\alpha(1 - R_0/R)} = -\frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(1 - R_0/R)} ; \quad \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = 0 \Rightarrow (R^2 E_r/h) + (dR/d\varphi)\alpha = 0$$

$$4^{\text{th}}\text{mode} : dz = \alpha dr - dr ; \text{ circular geodesics : } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(\alpha - 1)(1 - R_0/R)} ; \quad \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = 0 \Rightarrow dR = 0$$

$$\text{Let us set: } w = 1/R \Rightarrow 1^{\text{st}}\text{mode: } \frac{dw}{d\varphi} = 0 ; 2^{\text{nd}}\text{mode: } \frac{dw}{d\varphi} = -\frac{E_r}{\alpha h} ; 3^{\text{rd}}\text{mode: } \frac{dw}{d\varphi} = \frac{E_r}{\alpha h} ; 4^{\text{th}}\text{mode: } \frac{dw}{d\varphi} = 0 \quad (8.10)$$

The variable w is defined by the equation: $\frac{d^2 w}{d\varphi^2} + w - 3w^2 R_0/2 = \kappa R_0/(2h^2)$; this equation is verified approximately by

the relations (8.10) by taking into account the relation ($\omega \gg \pi/2$); on average: $dw/d\varphi = 0$.

Summary:

$$1^{\text{st}}\text{mode} : dz = \alpha dr + dr ; 2^{\text{nd}}\text{mode: } dz = \alpha dr + dt ; 3^{\text{rd}}\text{mode} : dz = \alpha dr - dt ; 4^{\text{th}}\text{mode} : dz = \alpha dr - dr$$

$$\text{circular geodesics: } 1^{\text{st}}\text{ mode} : \frac{d\varphi}{dt} = (\alpha + 1) \frac{(1 - R_0/R)}{(R^2 E_r/h)} ; 2^{\text{nd}} \text{ and } 3^{\text{rd}}\text{ modes} : \frac{d\varphi}{dt} = \alpha \frac{(1 - R_0/R)}{(R^2 E_r/h)} ; 4^{\text{th}}\text{mode} : \frac{d\varphi}{dt} = (\alpha - 1) \frac{(1 - R_0/R)}{(R^2 E_r/h)}$$

$$\text{On average : } dz = \frac{(\alpha dr + dr) + (\alpha dr + dt) + (\alpha dr - dt) + (\alpha dr - dr)}{4} = \alpha dr = \frac{dR}{(1 - R_0/R)} \quad (8.11)$$

$$\text{On average : } \frac{d\varphi}{dt} = \frac{(\alpha + 1) + 2\alpha + (\alpha - 1)}{4} \frac{(1 - R_0/R)}{(R^2 E_r/h)} = \alpha \frac{(1 - R_0/R)}{(R^2 E_r/h)} \Rightarrow \left[\frac{d\varphi}{\alpha dt} \right]_{\text{average}} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1 - R_0/R)} \quad (8.12)$$

On average, the metric (8.5) becomes:

$$ds^2 = \frac{(\alpha + 1)^2 + 2(\alpha^2 - 1) + (\alpha - 1)^2}{4} [1 - R_0/R(t,r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2 \Rightarrow$$

$$ds^2 = [1 - R_0/R(t,r)][(\alpha dt)^2 - (\alpha dr)^2] - [R(t,r)]^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2) ; \quad dz = \alpha dr = \frac{dR}{(1 - R_0/R)} \quad (8.13)$$

The average metric defined by the relations (8.13) is the classical Schwarzschild metric. Consequently, if ($\alpha > 1$), the metric (8.5) is a quasi-Schwarzschild metric, slightly disrupted by the triangular signal ($\omega \gg \pi/2$).

B/Second case: $1 > \alpha \geq 0$

In the metric (8.5), the coefficients of dt^2 and dr^2 permute continuously their sign over time. The temporal differentials of the coordinates have to be aligned on the real time, as we have to take into account the first integral: $R^2 \frac{d\varphi}{d\sigma} = h \Rightarrow$ variation of the φ angle with respect to the proper time is monotonic. Then, we have to change the sign of the temporal differentials in the 3rd and 4th modes for aligning them on the 1st mode that we set as the reference mode. By homogenizing the coordinate's symbols for obtaining in all modes dt as the temporal differential and dr as the spatial differential, we rewrite the metric (8.5) and the relations (8.6) to (8.9):

Metric:

$$1^{\text{st}} \text{ mode : } ds^2 = (1 + \alpha)^2 [1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2 \quad (8.14)$$

$$2^{\text{nd}} \text{ mode : } ds^2 = (1 - \alpha^2) [1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2 \quad (8.15)$$

$$3^{\text{rd}} \text{ mode : } ds^2 = (1 - \alpha^2) [1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2 \quad (8.16)$$

$$4^{\text{th}} \text{ mode : } ds^2 = (1 - \alpha)^2 [1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2 \quad (8.17)$$

$$1^{\text{st}} \text{ mode : } dz = \alpha dr + dr ; \text{ geodesic : } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(\alpha+1)(1-R_0/R)} ; \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(\alpha+1)(1-R_0/R)} ;$$

$$2^{\text{nd}} \text{ mode : } dz = \alpha dt + dr ; \text{ geodesic : } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{-(R^2 E_r/h) + (dR/d\varphi)\alpha}{(\alpha^2-1)(1-R_0/R)} ; \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)\alpha - (dR/d\varphi)}{(\alpha^2-1)(1-R_0/R)}$$

$$3^{\text{rd}} \text{ mode : } dz = -\alpha dt - dr ; \text{ geodesic : } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = -\frac{(R^2 E_r/h) + (dR/d\varphi)\alpha}{(\alpha^2-1)(1-R_0/R)} ; \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)\alpha + (dR/d\varphi)}{(\alpha^2-1)(1-R_0/R)}$$

$$4^{\text{th}} \text{ mode : } dz = \alpha dr - dr ; \text{ geodesic : } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = -\frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(\alpha-1)(1-R_0/R)} ; \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{(\alpha-1)(1-R_0/R)}$$

For the circular geodesics of a massive particle, we set: $dr = 0$

$$1^{\text{st}} \text{ mode : } \text{circular geodesics : } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(\alpha+1)(1-R_0/R)} ; \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = 0 \Rightarrow dR = 0$$

$$2^{\text{nd}} \text{ mode : } \text{circular geodesics : } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1-R_0/R)} = \frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{\alpha(1-R_0/R)} ; \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = 0 \Rightarrow (R^2 E_r/h)\alpha - (dR/d\varphi) = 0$$

$$3^{\text{rd}} \text{ mode : } \text{circular geodesics : } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1-R_0/R)} = -\frac{(dR/d\varphi)}{\alpha(1-R_0/R)} ; \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = 0 \Rightarrow (R^2 E_r/h)\alpha + (dR/d\varphi) = 0$$

$$4^{\text{th}} \text{ mode : } \text{circular geodesics : } \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)}{(1-\alpha)(1-R_0/R)} ; \frac{dr}{d\varphi} = 0 \Rightarrow dR = 0$$

$$\text{We set: } w = 1/R \Rightarrow 1^{\text{st}} \text{ mode: } \frac{dw}{d\varphi} = 0 ; 2^{\text{nd}} \text{ mode: } \frac{dw}{d\varphi} = -\frac{\alpha E_r}{h} ; 3^{\text{rd}} \text{ mode: } \frac{dw}{d\varphi} = \frac{\alpha E_r}{h} ; 4^{\text{th}} \text{ mode: } \frac{dw}{d\varphi} = 0 \quad (8.18)$$

The variable w is defined by the equation: $\frac{d^2 w}{d\varphi^2} + w - 3 w^2 R_0/2 = \kappa R_0/(2h^2)$; this equation is verified approximately by the relations (8.18) by taking into account the relation ($\omega \gg \pi/2$); on average: $dw/d\varphi = 0$.

Summary:

$$1^{\text{st}} \text{ mode : } dz = \alpha dr + dr ; 2^{\text{nd}} \text{ mode: } dz = \alpha dt + dr ; 3^{\text{rd}} \text{ mode : } dz = -\alpha dt - dr ; 4^{\text{th}} \text{ mode : } dz = \alpha dr - dr$$

$$\text{circular geodesics: } 1^{\text{st}} \text{ mode : } \frac{d\varphi}{dt} = (1 + \alpha) \frac{(1-R_0/R)}{(R^2 E_r/h)} ; 2^{\text{nd}} \text{ and } 3^{\text{rd}} \text{ modes : } \frac{d\varphi}{dt} = \frac{(1-R_0/R)}{(R^2 E_r/h)} ; 4^{\text{th}} \text{ mode : } \frac{d\varphi}{dt} = (1 - \alpha) \frac{(1-R_0/R)}{(R^2 E_r/h)}$$

$$\text{On average : } dz = \frac{(\alpha dr + dr) + (\alpha dt + dr) + (-\alpha dt - dr) + (\alpha dr - dr)}{4} = \frac{\alpha}{2} dr = \frac{dR}{(1-R_0/R)} \quad (8.19)$$

$$\text{On average : } \frac{d\varphi}{dt} = \frac{(1 + \alpha) + 2 + (1 - \alpha)}{4} \frac{(1-R_0/R)}{(R^2 E_r/h)} \Rightarrow \left[\frac{d\varphi}{dt} \right]_{\text{average}} = \frac{(1-R_0/R)}{(R^2 E_r/h)} \quad (8.20)$$

From the relations (8.14) to (8.17), on average, the metric (8.5) becomes:

$$ds^2 = \frac{(1+\alpha)^2 + 2(1-\alpha^2) + (1-\alpha)^2}{4} [1 - R_0/R(t, r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - \Omega^2 \Rightarrow$$

343 On average: $ds^2 = [1 - R_0/R(t,r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - [R(t,r)]^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2)$; $dz = \frac{\alpha}{2} dr = \frac{dR}{(1-R_0/R)}$ (8.21)

344 The average metric defined by the relations (8.21) is not the classical Schwarzschild metric. This metric could make the
345 transition between the metric with the bounded z function and the quasi-Schwarzschild metric.

346 The real time differential interval dT between two events located at (r, θ, φ) is:

347 $c dT = \sqrt{1 - R_0/R(t,r)} dt \approx dt$ (case: $R_0/R(t,r) \ll 1$) (8.22)

348 The real radial distance differential interval dL_r is:

349 $dL_r = \sqrt{1 - R_0/R(t,r)} dr \approx dr$ (case: $R_0/R(t,r) \ll 1$) (8.23)

350 We set: $\beta=2/\alpha$. From the relation (8.21), we obtain: $dr = \beta dR/(1-R_0/R)$. From the relation (8.23), we obtain:

351 $dL_r \approx \beta dR$ (case: $R_0/R(t,r) \ll 1$) (8.24)

352
353 From relations (4.9) and (8.20), we obtain on average: $\frac{d\varphi}{dt} = \frac{\sqrt{GM/c^2}}{R_s\sqrt{R_s}}$. The orbital velocity V_T of a massive particle
354 located on a circular orbit defined by $R = R_s$ is equal to: $(V_T)^2 = \frac{GM/R_s}{(1-R_0/R_s)}$. It follows that this last formula applies in the
355 whole galaxy.

357 9 The transient area in a galaxy according to MOND

358 We are not trying to do general reasoning concerning the profile of velocities of the stars in a galaxy, but only to
359 model approximately the velocity profile obtained by MOND.

360 We model the three areas defined in MOND: 1/ the Newton-Schwarzschild zone; 2/ the transition zone; 3/ the
361 asymptotic zone. The beginning of the MOND transient area is located at the radial distance L_A , and the end at the radial
362 distance L_B . By definition: $r_A = k_A R_C$, $r_B = k_B R_C$. In practice, as we are always in the case $R_0/R(t,r) \ll 1$, we have $r \approx L$.
363 Then, $L_A \approx k_A R_C$, $L_B \approx k_B R_C$. We set: $k_A \sim 0.4$; $k_B \sim 2.5$ (cf. §7).

364 We obtain: $R_A \approx L_A$, as we are also at the end of the Newtonian area. From the relation (8.24), in this transient
365 area, a radial distance $L(R)$ is obtained by the formula: $L \approx L_A + \beta(R - R_A) \Rightarrow$ It comes that, at the end of the transient
366 area: $L_B \approx L_A + \beta(R_C - L_A)$. We can deduce:

367 $\beta \approx \frac{L_B - L_A}{R_C - L_A} = \frac{k_B - k_A}{1 - k_A} \sim \frac{2.5 - 0.4}{1 - 0.4} = 3.5 \Rightarrow \alpha = \frac{2}{3.5} = 0.57$

368 $R \approx L_A + (L - L_A)/\beta \Rightarrow R \approx R_C[k_A + (L/R_C - k_A)/\beta]$

369 We deduce the orbital velocity of a star located at the distance L_s of the center of the galaxy ($k_A \leq L_s/R_C \leq k_B$).

370 $V_T = \sqrt{\frac{GM/R_s}{1 - R_0/R_s}} \approx \sqrt{\frac{GM/R_C}{k_A + (L_s/R_C - k_A)/\beta}} \approx \frac{V_{outM}}{\sqrt{k_A + (L_s/R_C - k_A)/\beta}}$ (9.1)

371 Deviation δ_R of the light rays is obtained by the classical relation: $\delta_R = \frac{4GM}{c^2 R}$. We deduce the following formula, where L is
372 the real distance:

373 $\delta_R = \frac{4GM/(c^2 R_C)}{k_A + (L/R_C - k_A)/\beta}$ ($k_A \leq L_s/R_C \leq k_B$) (9.2)

375 10 Summary of the metric according to MOND

376 The metric has the form:

377 $ds^2 = [1 - R_0/R(t,r)](dt^2 - dr^2) - [R(t,r)]^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2)$

378 $z = R(t,r) + R_0 \text{Log} |(R(t,r)/R_0) - 1|$

379 In the radial space of the galaxy there are three areas. Each area has a particular z function.

380 Let us set: $R_C = \sqrt{GM_b/a_0}$; $a_0 \sim 1.2 \times 10^{-10} m.s^{-2}$; $r_A = k_A R_C$; $r_B = k_B R_C$ where $k_A \sim 0.4$; $k_B \sim 2.5$

In all areas, the z function contains a High Frequency Triangular Signal with a null average (HFTS)

1st area: (quasi) Schwarzschild area ($\alpha > 1$): $r \leq r_A \Rightarrow z = r + \text{HFTS}$

2nd area: transition area ($\alpha \sim 0.57$): $r_A < r < r_B \Rightarrow z = r_A + (r - r_A) \alpha/2 + \text{HFTS}$

3rd area: asymptotic area ($\alpha = 0$): $r \geq r_B \Rightarrow z = R_C + \text{HFTS}$

Neglecting the ratio: $R_0/R(t, r)$, we obtain the radial distance L : $L \approx r \Rightarrow L_A \approx r_A$; $L_B \approx r_B$

The orbital velocity V_T of stars moving on a circular orbit defined by $R = R_s$ is: $V_T \approx \sqrt{GM/R_s(L)}$.

Deviation of light rays is obtained by the formula: $\delta_R = 4GM/[c^2R(L)]$.

$R(L)$ is the function obtained from $R(t, r)$ by neglecting the HTFS signal and the ratio: R_0/R .

1st area: $R(L) = L$; 2nd area: $R(L) = L_A + (L - L_A) \alpha/2$; 3rd area: $R(L) = R_C$

We observe a significant difference between the MOND theory and our interpretation of MOND:

In the MOND theory, the local radial acceleration a_r is equal to $a_r = (V_T)^2/L$ in the whole domain of the galaxy; local acceleration is calculated with respect to the distance L : the distance from the center of the galaxy. In the asymptotic area: $a_f = V_{\text{outM}}^2/L = \sqrt{GM_b a_0}/L$: the acceleration decreases in $1/L$.

In our interpretation of MOND, the concept of acceleration is not used in the calculations. The orbital velocity of a massive particle uses the average local value of the $R(t, r)$, which is constant in the asymptotic area. By neglecting the triangular signal and the ratio: R_0/R , we can evaluate a local radial acceleration $a_r = GM_b/[R(L)]^2 = (V_T)^2/R(L)$, valid for the whole galaxy; it follows that in the asymptotic area, we obtain: $a_r = a_0$. In our solution, the Milgrom constant a_0 is the lowest possible acceleration value in a galaxy: the radial acceleration decreases only if an external gravitational field modifies the internal gravitational field of the galaxy.

11 Physical conjectures

We now propose a set of physical conjectures for justifying our mathematical model.

1/ The gravitational field in a galaxy can be modeled by General Relativity without dark matter.

2/ In a central symmetric gravitational field in finite vacuum space, the Riemann curvature has a lower bound; then, the Kretschmann scalar Kr has a lower bound: $Kr_{\min} = Ckr/M_b$, where M_b is the baryonic mass of the central body and Ckr is a constant scalar: $Ckr \sim 1.5 \times 10^{-52} Kg \cdot m^{-4}$. This limit creates an asymptotic area in periphery of the finite space; this area extends as far as we want if there is no external gravitational field. In the asymptotic area, the radial acceleration a_r is constant: $a_r = a_0$, where a_0 is the Milgrom acceleration constant, which in fact should have to be deduced from the constant number Ckr by the formula $a_0 = Ckr \left(\frac{c^4 G}{48}\right)^{1/3}$; the orbital velocity V_T of stars in the area is constant: $(V_T)^4 \approx G M_b a_0$. The R function, defined by a triangular signal, oscillates at high frequency, with a constant value equal to $R_C \approx \sqrt{GM_b/a_0}$ (the R value remains constant due to the incessant permutation of the temporal/spatial role of the t, r coordinates).

3/ The pulsation ω of the triangular signal is assumed to have a high value ($\omega \gg \pi/2$), which allows to make the assumption that the geodesic of a particle can be approximately calculated by the average formulae combining the four modes of oscillation of the metric. The calculation of the true geodesic of a particle, taking into account the temporal behavior of the metric is far more complicated, and could perhaps lead to the conclusion that the true geodesic is in practice unpredictable, being too sensitive to the initial conditions. This could suggest the existence of a relationship between the metric and quantum mechanics: the pulsation ω could perhaps be deduced from the set of constant numbers arising in quantum mechanics.

4/ We are coming back to the definition of the bounds of the transition area. Based on the MOND theory data, the beginning of the transient area has been defined at the distance $L_A = k_A R_C$. So, we have made the assumption that the α

422 coefficient, characterizing the hybrid metric, changes its value, and becomes higher than 1 if the Kretschmann scalar is
423 higher than a particular value $Kr_{trans} \Rightarrow$ If $Kr > Kr_{trans} \Rightarrow \alpha > 1$; $Kr_{trans} = (R_C/R_A)^6 Kr_{min} = (1/k_A)^6 Kr_{min}$.

$$424 \quad Kr_{trans} \sim (1/0.4)^6 \times 1.5 \times 10^{-52}/M_b \quad (11.1)$$

425 5/ The constant scalar α (in the transient area) is set to a value close to $\frac{1}{2}$ ($\alpha \sim 0.57$ according to the MOND data).

427 12 Conclusion

428 In the framework of General Relativity, in a finite vacuum spherical space, we have obtained a non static metric, in
429 which the Riemann space-time curvature oscillates continuously; the average formulation of this metric allows recovering
430 in a galaxy, without any dark matter, a star velocity profile similar to the velocity profile calculated in the MOND theory.
431 Consequently, this result allows finding the Tully-Fisher law in the framework of General Relativity without any dark
432 matter. The asymptotic behavior of this metric is due to the existence of a lower bound of the space-time Riemann
433 curvature. The radial acceleration obtained in our solution is quite different from the radial acceleration postulated in the
434 MOND theory; particularly, in the asymptotic area of our solution, the radial acceleration has a lower bound equal to the
435 Milgrom constant a_0 . On a physical point of view, we have not justified both parameters defining the transient area of a
436 galaxy. In future developments, we will have to analyze this point. We suspect that the geodesic of a particle calculated
437 with the true metric could be unpredictable in practice, which could perhaps allow establishing a relationship between the
438 true metric and quantum mechanics, particularly for defining the value of the frequency invoked in the true metric. We
439 will have also to analyze this point in future developments.

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Appendix A

Calculating the non static metric

In the mathematic expressions of the appendices, the exponents t, r define the partial derivatives with respect to the t, r coordinates. The exponents u, v, z, R define the full derivatives with respect to functions u, v, z, R . R_0 is defined by the relation: $R_0 = 2GM/c^2$.

1 The Ricci tensor

For the space-time interval: $ds^2 = e^{2\nu(t,r)}dt^2 - e^{2\lambda(t,r)}dr^2 - [R(t,r)]^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2)$, the Ricci tensor components different from zero are defined by the following expressions:

$$R_{00} = v^t(\lambda^t + 2R^t/R) - (\lambda^t\lambda^t + \lambda^{tt} + 2R^{tt}/R) + e^{2\nu-2\lambda}[v^{rr} + v^r(v^r - \lambda^r) + 2v^rR^r/R] = 0 \quad (A1.1)$$

$$R_{11} = \lambda^r(v^r + 2R^r/R) - (v^rv^r + v^{rr} + 2R^{rr}/R) + e^{2\lambda-2\nu}[\lambda^{tt} - \lambda^t(v^t - \lambda^t) + 2\lambda^tR^t/R] = 0 \quad (A1.2)$$

$$R_{22} = 1 + e^{-2\nu}[R^{tt}R + R^tR^t - R^tR(v^t - \lambda^t)] - e^{-2\lambda}[R^{rr}R + R^rR^r + R^rR(v^r - \lambda^r)] = 0 \quad (A1.3)$$

$$R_{33} = \sin^2\theta\{1 + e^{-2\nu}[R^{tt}R + R^tR^t - R^tR(v^t - \lambda^t)] - e^{-2\lambda}[R^{rr}R + R^rR^r + R^rR(v^r - \lambda^r)]\} = 0 \quad (A1.4)$$

$$R_{01} = R_{10} = (2/R)(-R^{tr} + v^rR^t + \lambda^tR^r) = 0 \quad (A1.5)$$

By setting $R(t,r) = r$, we can verify that we obtain the Ricci tensor leading to the definition of the classical Schwarzschild metric. Now, instead of setting: $R(t,r) = r$, we set $\lambda(t,r) = \nu(t,r)$. We make this choice for obtaining a Schwarzschild metric in tortoise coordinates, extended in the temporal domain. We neglect the R_{33} component, which is proportional to R_{22} , and we multiply each tensor component by a convenient term, for obtaining the following new set of four equations:

$$ds^2 = e^{2\nu(t,r)}dt^2 - e^{2\nu(t,r)}dr^2 - [R(t,r)]^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2) \quad (A1.6)$$

$$R R_{00} = 2v^tR^t - Rv^{tt} - 2R^{tt} + Rv^{rr} + 2v^rR^r = 0 \quad (A1.7)$$

$$R R_{11} = 2v^rR^r - Rv^{rr} - 2R^{rr} + Rv^{tt} + 2v^tR^t = 0 \quad (A1.8)$$

$$e^{2\nu} R_{22} = e^{2\nu} + (R^tR^t + RR^{tt}) - (R^{rr}R + R^rR^r) = 0 \quad (A1.9)$$

$$(R/2) R_{01} = -R^{tr} + v^rR^t + v^tR^r = 0 \quad (A1.10)$$

We perform two combinations of equations (A1.7) and (A1.8):

The opposite of half-sum: equation (A1.7)/2 + equation (A1.8)/2 and its consequences

$$-2v^tR^t + R^{tt} - 2v^rR^r + R^{rr} = 0 \Rightarrow e^{-2\nu}(-2v^tR^t + R^{tt}) + e^{-2\nu}(-2v^rR^r + R^{rr}) = 0 \Rightarrow (R^te^{-2\nu})^t + (R^re^{-2\nu})^r = 0$$

The half-difference: equation (A1.7)/2 - equation (A1.8)/2

$$-Rv^{tt} - R^{tt} + Rv^{rr} + R^{rr} = 0$$

$$\text{From equation (A1.9)} \Rightarrow e^{2\nu} + (R^tR^t + RR^{tt}) - (R^{rr}R + R^rR^r) = 0 \Rightarrow (RR^r)^r - (RR^t)^t = e^{2\nu}$$

Let us set an arbitrary two times differentiable function $F(t,r)$; we obtain the final set of four equations:

$$(R^te^{-2\nu} + F^r)^t + (R^re^{-2\nu} - F^t)^r = 0 \quad (A1.11)$$

$$(RR^r)^r - (RR^t)^t - e^{2\nu} = 0 \quad (A1.12)$$

$$R^{tt} - R^{rr} + Rv^{tt} - Rv^{rr} = 0 \quad (A1.13)$$

$$-R^{tr} + v^rR^t + v^tR^r = 0 \quad (A1.14)$$

2 Solving equations (A1.11) and (A1.14)

The F function being arbitrary, we can split the equation (A1.11) by setting both equations (A2.1):

$$(R^te^{-2\nu} + F^r) = 0 \quad ; \quad (R^re^{-2\nu} - F^t) = 0 \quad (A2.1)$$

$$R^t = -F^re^{2\nu} \quad ; \quad R^r = F^te^{2\nu} \quad (A2.2)$$

$$R^tF^t + R^rF^r = 0 \quad (A2.3)$$

Let us calculate the derivatives of relations (A2.2) and replace in equation (A1.14) R^t and R^r by their values.

$$R^{tr} = -F^{rr}e^{2\nu} - 2v^rF^re^{2\nu} = R^{tr} = F^{tt}e^{2\nu} + 2v^tF^te^{2\nu} = -v^rF^re^{2\nu} + v^tF^te^{2\nu} \Rightarrow F^{tt} = F^{rr} = -v^rF^r - v^tF^t$$

$$F^{tt} - F^{rr} = 0 \quad (A2.4)$$

Let us set : $u = t+r$; $v = t-r \Rightarrow FP(u)$ and $FM(v)$ being two unknown two times differentiable functions, we obtain:

$$F = FP(u) + FM(v) \Rightarrow F^t = FP^u + FM^v ; F^r = FP^u - FM^v \Rightarrow \rho = (F^t)^2 - (F^r)^2 = 4FP^u FM^v \quad (A2.5)$$

Rewriting the equation (A2.3) in coordinates (u, v) instead of (t, r) :

$$R^t F^t + R^r F^r = 0 \Rightarrow \left[\left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial u} \right)_v + \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial v} \right)_u \right] (FP^u + FM^v) + \left[\left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial u} \right)_v - \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial v} \right)_u \right] (FP^u - FM^v) = 0 \Rightarrow \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial u} \right)_v FP^u + \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial v} \right)_u FM^v = 0$$

$$\text{Let us set : } HP^u = 1/(4 FP^u) ; HM^v = 1/(4 FM^v) \Rightarrow \frac{\left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial u} \right)_v}{4 HP^u} + \frac{\left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial v} \right)_u}{4 HM^v} = 0 \quad (A2.6)$$

$$4HP^u HM^v = 1/(4FP^u FM^v) = 1/\rho$$

Rewriting the equation (A2.6) in coordinates (HP, HM) instead of (u, v) :

$$\left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial u} \right)_v = \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial HP} \right)_{HM} HP^u ; \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial v} \right)_u = \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial HM} \right)_{HP} HM^v \Rightarrow \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial HP} \right)_{HM} + \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial HM} \right)_{HP} = 0 \quad (A2.7)$$

The solution of equation (A2.7) is an arbitrary function of the z parameter defined hereafter:

$$z = HP(u) - HM(v) \quad (A2.8)$$

$$R = R(z) \quad (A2.9)$$

$$z^t = HP^u - HM^v ; z^r = HP^u + HM^v \Rightarrow z^{tt} - z^{rr} = 0 ; (z^r)^2 - (z^t)^2 = 4HP^u HM^v = 1/\rho \quad (A2.10)$$

$$R = R(z) \Rightarrow R^t = R^z (HP^u - HM^v) ; R^r = R^z (HP^u + HM^v) \quad (A2.11)$$

$$\text{From relations (A2.2): } e^{2v} = -R^t/F^r = -R^z \frac{HP^u - HM^v}{FP^u - FM^v} = -R^z \frac{HP^u - HM^v}{\left(\frac{1}{4HP^u} - \frac{1}{4HM^v} \right)}$$

$$e^{2v} = 4 HP^u HM^v R^z = R^z/\rho \quad (A2.12)$$

3 Solving the equation (A1.12)

$$(RR^r)^r - (RR^t)^t - e^{2v} = 0 \Rightarrow (RR^z z^r)^r - (RR^z z^t)^t - R^z/\rho = 0 \Rightarrow$$

$$(RR^z)^z z^r z^r + RR^z z^{rr} - (RR^z)^z z^t z^t - RR^z z^{tt} - R^z/\rho = 0 \Rightarrow (RR^z)^z (z^r z^r - z^t z^t) + RR^z (z^{rr} - z^{tt}) - R^z/\rho = 0 \Rightarrow$$

$$(RR^z)^z/\rho - R^z/\rho = 0 \Rightarrow (RR^z)^z - R^z = 0 \Rightarrow RR^z - R = -R_0 \Rightarrow R^z = (1 - R_0/R) \quad (A3.1)$$

$$e^{2v} = 4 HP^u HM^v R^z = 4 HP^u HM^v (1 - R_0/R) \quad (A3.2)$$

At the limit of the static metric, we obtain: $HP^u = HM^v = 1/2$.

$$R^z = dR/dz = (1 - R_0/R) \Rightarrow dz = dR/(1 - R_0/R) \Rightarrow \quad (A3.3)$$

$$z = HP(u) - HM(v) = R + R_0 \text{Log} |R/R_0 - 1| \quad (A3.4)$$

The relation (A3.4) allows determining implicitly the $R(t, r)$ function as a function of the two differentiable functions $HP(u)$ and $HM(v)$.

In the case of the static metric: $HP(u) = (t+r)/2$, $HM(v) = (t-r)/2 \Rightarrow z = r$. The relation (A3.2) defines $e^{2v(t, r)}$; the definition of the non static metric is completed, but we have to verify the equation (A1.13).

4 Verification of the equation (A1.13): $R^{tt} - R^{rr} + Rv^{tt} - Rv^{rr} = 0$

$$\text{from relation (A2.9)} \Rightarrow R^t = R^z z^t ; R^r = R^z z^r \Rightarrow R^{tt} = R^{zz} z^t z^t + R^z z^{tt} ; R^{rr} = R^{zz} z^r z^r + R^z z^{rr} \quad (A4.1)$$

$$z^{rr} - z^{tt} = 0 ; (z^r)^2 - (z^t)^2 = 1/\rho ; R^{tt} - R^{rr} = R^{zz} (z^t z^t - z^r z^r) + R^z (z^{tt} - z^{rr}) \Rightarrow R^{tt} - R^{rr} = -R^{zz}/\rho \quad (A4.2)$$

$$\text{from relations (A2.13)} \Rightarrow e^{2v} = 4 HP^u HM^v R^z \Rightarrow 2v = \text{Log}(R^z) + \text{Log}(2HP^u) + \text{Log}(2HM^v) \quad (A4.3)$$

$$2v^t = (R^{zz}/R^z) z^t + (HP^{uu}/HP^u) + (HM^{vv}/HM^v) \Rightarrow 2v^{tt} = (R^{zz}/R^z)^z z^t z^t + (R^{zz}/R^z) z^{tt} + (HP^{uu}/HP^u)^u + (HM^{vv}/HM^v)^v \quad (A4.4)$$

$$2v^r = (R^{zz}/R^z) z^r + (HP^{uu}/HP^u) - (HM^{vv}/HM^v) \Rightarrow 2v^{rr} = (R^{zz}/R^z)^z z^r z^r + (R^{zz}/R^z) z^{rr} + (HP^{uu}/HP^u)^u + (HM^{vv}/HM^v)^v \quad (A4.5)$$

$$Rv^{tt} - Rv^{rr} = (R^{zz}/R^z)^z (z^t z^t - z^r z^r) R/2 + (R^{zz}/R^z) (z^{tt} - z^{rr}) R/2 = -(R/2\rho) (R^{zz}/R^z)^z \quad (A4.6)$$

$$R^{tt} - R^{rr} + Rv^{tt} - Rv^{rr} = -R^{zz}/\rho - (R/2\rho) (R^{zz}/R^z)^z = -(1/2\rho) [2R^{zz} + (R R^{zz}/R^z)^z - R^z R^{zz}/R^z] =$$

$$= -(1/2\rho) [R^z + R R^{zz}/R^z]^z = -(1/2\rho) [(RR^z)^z/R^z]^z = 0 \quad \{ (RR^z)^z = R^z \text{ from relations(A3.1)} \}$$

$$R^{tt} - R^{rr} + Rv^{tt} - Rv^{rr} = 0$$

5 Summary of the non static metric

Let us set $u = t+r$, $v = t-r$, $HP(u)$, $HP(v)$, $R_0 = 2GM/c^2$.

532 HP(u) and HM(v) are arbitrary two times differentiable functions.

533
$$ds^2 = e^{2\nu(t,r)}dt^2 - e^{2\nu(t,r)}dr^2 - [R(t,r)]^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2)$$

534
$$e^{2\nu} = 4 HP^u HM^v(1 - R_0/R) \tag{A5.1}$$

535
$$z = HP(u) - HM(v) = R + R_0 \text{Log} |R/R_0 - 1| \tag{A5.2}$$

536 The R(t,r) function is implicitly defined by the relation (A5.2). A priori, we have to deduce the functions HP(u) and
537 HM(v) from the boundary conditions (one upstream and one downstream); but we have another possibility: a physical
538 law forcing the R(t,r) value. The spatial domain of the non static metric is finite. Due to the wave equation: $z^{tt} - z^{rr} = 0$,
539 internal self-maintained waves are possible in the finite space.

540 The Kretschmann scalar Kr: $Kr = \mathbf{R}^{abcd}\mathbf{R}_{abcd}$ obtained from the Riemann tensor \mathbf{R} , is equal to:

541
$$Kr = 48 G^2 M^2 / \{c^4 [R(t,r)]^6\} \tag{A5.3}$$

Appendix B

Geodesics first integrals

Let us set : $\kappa = 1$ for the massive particles, $\kappa = 0$ for the particles without mass, $w = 1/R$; $R_0 = 2 G M/c^2$

Let us set: E_r : the particle energy, h : the particle angular momentum.

1 Geodesics of the non static metric

The Christoffel numbers different from zero are:

$$\Gamma_{00}^0 = \Gamma_{11}^0 = v^t; \Gamma_{01}^0 = \Gamma_{10}^0 = v^r; \Gamma_{22}^0 = e^{-2\nu}RR^t; \Gamma_{33}^0 = e^{-2\nu}RR^t\sin^2\theta$$

$$\Gamma_{00}^1 = \Gamma_{11}^1 = v^r; \Gamma_{01}^1 = \Gamma_{10}^1 = v^t; \Gamma_{22}^1 = -e^{-2\nu}RR^r; \Gamma_{33}^1 = -e^{-2\nu}RR^r\sin^2\theta$$

$$\Gamma_{02}^2 = \Gamma_{20}^2 = R^t/R; \Gamma_{12}^2 = \Gamma_{21}^2 = R^r/R; \Gamma_{33}^2 = -\sin\theta\cos\theta$$

$$\Gamma_{03}^3 = \Gamma_{30}^3 = R^t/R; \Gamma_{13}^3 = \Gamma_{31}^3 = R^r/R; \Gamma_{23}^3 = \Gamma_{32}^3 = \cotg\theta$$

The geodesics are defined by the following equation: $\frac{d^2x^\lambda}{d\sigma^2} + \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^\lambda \frac{dx^\mu}{d\sigma} \frac{dx^\nu}{d\sigma} = 0$

σ is the proper time in meters ($\sigma = c\tau$) where τ is the proper time in sec. for a massive particle, and an affine parameter for a particle without mass. In this appendix, the σ, φ exponents define the full derivatives with respect to the σ, φ parameters. Using the Christoffel numbers, we obtain the four geodesics equations:

$$t^{\sigma\sigma} + v^t(t^\sigma)^2 + 2v^r t^\sigma r^\sigma + v^t(r^\sigma)^2 + e^{-2\nu}RR^t(\theta^\sigma)^2 + e^{-2\nu}RR^t\sin^2\theta(\varphi^\sigma)^2 = 0 \quad (B1.1)$$

$$r^{\sigma\sigma} + v^r(t^\sigma)^2 + 2v^t t^\sigma r^\sigma + v^r(r^\sigma)^2 - e^{-2\nu}RR^r(\theta^\sigma)^2 - e^{-2\nu}RR^r\sin^2\theta(\varphi^\sigma)^2 = 0 \quad (B1.2)$$

$$\theta^{\sigma\sigma} + 2(R^t/R)t^\sigma\theta^\sigma + 2(R^r/R)r^\sigma\theta^\sigma - \sin\theta\cos\theta(\varphi^\sigma)^2 = 0 \quad (B1.3)$$

$$\varphi^{\sigma\sigma} + 2(R^t/R)t^\sigma\varphi^\sigma + 2(R^r/R)r^\sigma\varphi^\sigma + 2\cotg\theta\theta^\sigma\varphi^\sigma = 0 \quad (B1.4)$$

Simple transformations lead to the following relations:

$$(R^2\theta^\sigma)^\sigma - R^2\sin\theta\cos\theta(\varphi^\sigma)^2 = 0 \quad (B1.5)$$

$$(R^2\sin^2\theta\varphi^\sigma)^\sigma = 0 \Rightarrow R^2\sin^2\theta\varphi^\sigma = h \quad (B1.6)$$

Due to the symmetry of the problem, the trajectory is contained in a plane; we set: $\theta = \pi/2$ (the usual choice). We obtain two relations:

$$\theta = \pi/2 \quad (B1.7)$$

$$R^2\varphi^\sigma = h \quad (B1.8)$$

From the space-time interval: $ds^2 = e^{2\nu}dt^2 - e^{2\nu}dr^2 - R^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2)$, we obtain the following first integral:

$$e^{2\nu}(t^\sigma)^2 - e^{2\nu}(r^\sigma)^2 - (h^2/R^2) = \kappa \Rightarrow (t^\sigma)^2 - (r^\sigma)^2 = e^{-2\nu}[(h^2/R^2) + \kappa] \quad (B1.9)$$

For obtaining the last first integrals, we make the following calculations:

Equations (B1.1) and (B1.2) are rewritten:

$$t^{\sigma\sigma} + 2v^t(t^\sigma)^2 + 2v^r r^\sigma t^\sigma + v^t[(r^\sigma)^2 - (t^\sigma)^2] + e^{-2\nu}RR^t(h^2/R^4) = 0 \quad (B1.10)$$

$$r^{\sigma\sigma} + 2v^t t^\sigma r^\sigma + 2v^r(r^\sigma)^2 - v^r[(r^\sigma)^2 - (t^\sigma)^2] - e^{-2\nu}RR^r(h^2/R^4) = 0 \quad (B1.11)$$

$$e^{2\nu}t^{\sigma\sigma} + 2e^{2\nu}v^\sigma t^\sigma + e^{-2\nu}\{-v^t e^{2\nu}[(h^2/R^2) + \kappa] + e^{2\nu}RR^t(h^2/R^4)\} = 0 \Rightarrow (e^{2\nu}t^\sigma)^\sigma - (e^{-2\nu}/2)\{e^{2\nu}[(h^2/R^2) + \kappa]\}^t = 0 \quad (B1.12)$$

$$e^{2\nu}r^{\sigma\sigma} + 2e^{2\nu}v^\sigma r^\sigma + e^{-2\nu}\{v^r e^{2\nu}[(h^2/R^2) + \kappa] - e^{2\nu}RR^r(h^2/R^4)\} = 0 \Rightarrow (e^{2\nu}r^\sigma)^\sigma + (e^{-2\nu}/2)\{e^{2\nu}[(h^2/R^2) + \kappa]\}^r = 0 \quad (B1.13)$$

$$e^{2\nu} = (1 - R_0/R)/\rho; \text{ soit : } \Omega = (1 - R_0/R)[(h^2/R^2) + \kappa] = \rho e^{2\nu}[(h^2/R^2) + \kappa] \Rightarrow$$

$$\Omega/\rho = e^{2\nu}[(h^2/R^2) + \kappa] \quad (B1.14)$$

$$2(e^{2\nu}t^\sigma)^\sigma - e^{-2\nu}(\Omega/\rho)^t = 0 \quad (B1.15a)$$

$$2(e^{2\nu}r^\sigma)^\sigma + e^{-2\nu}(\Omega/\rho)^r = 0 \quad (B1.15b)$$

Multiplying the equation (B1.15a) by $-F^r$, the equation (B1.15b) by F^t and adding, we obtain:

$$-2F^r(e^{2\nu}t^\sigma)^\sigma + e^{-2\nu}F^r(\Omega/\rho)^t + 2F^t(e^{2\nu}r^\sigma)^\sigma + e^{-2\nu}F^t(\Omega/\rho)^r = 0 \Rightarrow \quad (B1.16)$$

$$(-2F^r e^{2\nu t^\sigma} + 2F^t e^{2\nu r^\sigma})^\sigma + 2e^{2\nu} (F^r)^\sigma t^\sigma - 2e^{2\nu} (F^t)^\sigma r^\sigma + e^{-2\nu} F^r (\Omega/\rho)^t + e^{-2\nu} F^t (\Omega/\rho)^r = 0 \quad (\text{B1.17})$$

584 $R^t = -F^r e^{2\nu}$; $R^r = F^t e^{2\nu}$; $dR = -F^r e^{2\nu} dt + F^t e^{2\nu} dr$; the equation (B1.17) becomes:

$$2R^{\sigma\sigma} + 2e^{2\nu} (F^r)^\sigma t^\sigma - 2e^{2\nu} (F^t)^\sigma r^\sigma + e^{-2\nu} F^r [(\Omega^R/\rho)R^t - (\Omega/\rho^2)\rho^t] + e^{-2\nu} F^t [(\Omega^R/\rho)R^r - (\Omega/\rho^2)\rho^r] = 0 \quad (\text{B1.18})$$

$$2e^{2\nu} (F^r)^\sigma t^\sigma - 2e^{2\nu} (F^t)^\sigma r^\sigma = 2e^{2\nu} (F^{rt} t^\sigma + F^{rr} r^\sigma) t^\sigma - 2e^{2\nu} (F^{tt} t^\sigma + F^{tr} r^\sigma) r^\sigma = 2F^{rt} [(h^2/R^2) + \kappa]$$

$$\text{From relations (A2.5): } \rho = (F^t)^2 - (F^r)^2 \Rightarrow \rho^t = 2F^t F^{tt} - 2F^r F^{rt} ; \rho^r = 2F^t F^{tr} - 2F^r F^{rr}$$

$$e^{-2\nu} (\Omega/\rho^2) (\rho^t F^r + \rho^r F^t) = 2e^{-2\nu} e^{2\nu} \rho [(h^2/R^2) + \kappa] [(F^t F^{tt} - F^r F^{tr}) F^r + (F^t F^{tr} - F^r F^{rr}) F^t] / \rho^2 = 2F^{tr} [(h^2/R^2) + \kappa]$$

589 The equation (B1.17) becomes:

$$2R^{\sigma\sigma} + 2F^{tr} [(h^2/R^2) + \kappa] + \Omega^R - 2F^{tr} [(h^2/R^2) + \kappa] = 0 \Rightarrow 2R^{\sigma\sigma} + \Omega^R = 0 \Rightarrow 2R^\sigma R^{\sigma\sigma} + \Omega^R R^\sigma = 0 \Rightarrow \quad (\text{B1.19})$$

$$[(R^\sigma)^2]^\sigma + \Omega^\sigma = 0 \Rightarrow (R^\sigma)^2 + \Omega = (E_r)^2 \quad (\text{B1.20})$$

$$(R^\sigma)^2 + (1 - R_0/R) [(h^2/R^2) + \kappa] = (E_r)^2 \quad (\text{B1.21})$$

593 This relation is identical to the corresponding relation of the atic metric. We obtain a Binet equation:

$$(R^2 \varphi^\sigma w^\sigma \sigma^\varphi)^2 + (1 - R_0 w) (h^2 w^2 + \kappa) = (E_r)^2 \quad (\text{B1.22})$$

$$\text{De } R^2 \varphi^\sigma = h \Rightarrow h^2 (w^\varphi)^2 + (1 - R_0 w) (h^2 w^2 + \kappa) = (E_r)^2 \quad (\text{B1.23})$$

$$2h^2 w^\varphi w^\varphi + w^\varphi (2h^2 w - 3w^2 h^2 R_0 - \kappa R_0) = 0 \quad (\text{B1.24})$$

$$w^\varphi w^\varphi + w - 3w^2 R_0/2 = \kappa [R_0/(2h^2)] \quad (\text{B1.25})$$

598 We calculate now the last first integral:

$$\text{From equations (B1.15): } 2F^t (e^{2\nu t^\sigma})^\sigma - e^{-2\nu} F^t (\Omega/\rho)^t = 0 ; 2F^r (e^{2\nu r^\sigma})^\sigma + e^{-2\nu} F^r (\Omega/\rho)^r = 0 \Rightarrow \quad (\text{B1.26})$$

$$(2F^t e^{2\nu t^\sigma})^\sigma - 2e^{2\nu} (F^t)^\sigma t^\sigma - e^{-2\nu} F^t (\Omega/\rho)^t - (2F^r e^{2\nu r^\sigma})^\sigma + 2e^{2\nu} (F^r)^\sigma r^\sigma - e^{-2\nu} F^r (\Omega/\rho)^r = 0 \Rightarrow \quad (\text{B1.27})$$

$$[2e^{2\nu} (F^t t^\sigma - F^r r^\sigma)]^\sigma - 2e^{2\nu} [(F^t)^\sigma t^\sigma - (F^r)^\sigma r^\sigma] - e^{-2\nu} F^t (\Omega/\rho)^t - e^{-2\nu} F^r (\Omega/\rho)^r = 0 \quad (\text{B1.28})$$

$$(F^t)^\sigma t^\sigma - (F^r)^\sigma r^\sigma = t^\sigma (F^{tt} t^\sigma + F^{tr} r^\sigma) - r^\sigma (F^{rt} t^\sigma + F^{rr} r^\sigma) = F^{tt} (t^\sigma t^\sigma - r^\sigma r^\sigma) = F^{tt} e^{-2\nu} [(h^2/R^2) + \kappa] \quad (\text{B1.29})$$

$$e^{-2\nu} F^r (\Omega/\rho)^r + e^{-2\nu} F^t (\Omega/\rho)^t = e^{-2\nu} F^r [(\Omega^R/\rho)R^r - (\Omega/\rho^2)\rho^r] + e^{-2\nu} F^t [(\Omega^R/\rho)R^t - (\Omega/\rho^2)\rho^t] = \\ = e^{-2\nu} F^r [(\Omega^R/\rho)F^t e^{2\nu} - (\Omega/\rho^2)\rho^r] + e^{-2\nu} F^t [-(\Omega^R/\rho)F^r e^{2\nu} - (\Omega/\rho^2)\rho^t]$$

$$e^{-2\nu} F^r (\Omega/\rho^2)^r + e^{-2\nu} F^t (\Omega/\rho^2)^t = -e^{-2\nu} (\Omega/\rho^2) (\rho^r F^r + \rho^t F^t) = -e^{-2\nu} e^{2\nu} [(h^2/R^2) + \kappa] (\rho^r F^r + \rho^t F^t) / \rho \quad (\text{B1.30})$$

$$\text{From relations (A2.5): } \rho = (F^t)^2 - (F^r)^2 \Rightarrow \rho^t = 2F^t F^{tt} - 2F^r F^{rt} ; \rho^r = 2F^t F^{tr} - 2F^r F^{rr}$$

$$(\rho^r F^r + \rho^t F^t) = 2F^r (F^t F^{tr} - F^r F^{rr}) + 2F^t (F^t F^{tt} - F^r F^{rt}) = 2F^{tt} \rho \quad (\text{B1.31})$$

$$e^{-2\nu} F^r (\Omega/\rho^2)^r + e^{-2\nu} F^t (\Omega/\rho^2)^t = -2F^{tt} [(h^2/R^2) + \kappa] \quad (\text{B1.32})$$

$$\text{From relations: (B1.28), (B1.29), (B1.32): } [2e^{2\nu} (F^t t^\sigma - F^r r^\sigma)]^\sigma - 2F^{tt} [(h^2/R^2) + \kappa] + 2F^{tt} [(h^2/R^2) + \kappa] = 0$$

$$[2e^{2\nu} (F^t t^\sigma - F^r r^\sigma)]^\sigma = 0 \Rightarrow e^{2\nu} (F^t t^\sigma - F^r r^\sigma) = E_r$$

$$[2e^{2\nu} (F^t t^\sigma - F^r r^\sigma)]^\sigma = 0 \Rightarrow e^{2\nu} (F^t t^\sigma - F^r r^\sigma) = E_r ; E_r \text{ is the particle energy}$$

$$4HP^u HM^v (1 - R_0/R) (F^t t^\varphi - F^r r^\varphi) = R^2 E_r / h$$

$$z = HP^u - HM^v ; \Rightarrow z^\varphi = HP^u u^\varphi - HM^v v^\varphi = R^\varphi / (1 - R_0/R) \quad \{ \text{from relation (A3.3)} \}$$

$$t^\varphi (HP^u + HM^v) + (HP^u - HM^v) r^\varphi = (R^2 E_r / h) / (1 - R_0/R) ; t^\varphi (HP^u - HM^v) + r^\varphi (HP^u + HM^v) = R^\varphi / (1 - R_0/R)$$

$$2HP^u u^\varphi = [(R^2 E_r / h) + R^\varphi] / (1 - R_0/R) ; 2HM^v v^\varphi = [(R^2 E_r / h) - R^\varphi] / (1 - R_0/R)$$

2 Summary of the first integrals:

$$\theta = \pi/2 \quad (\text{B2.1})$$

$$R^2 d\varphi/d\sigma = h \quad (\text{B2.2})$$

$$(R^\sigma)^2 + (1 - R_0/R) [(h^2/R^2) + \kappa] = (E_r)^2 \quad (\text{B2.3})$$

$$w^\varphi w^\varphi + w - 3w^2 G M / c^2 = \kappa G M / h^2 c^2 \quad (\text{B2.4})$$

$$e^{2\nu} (F^t t^\sigma - F^r r^\sigma) = E_r \quad (\text{B2.5})$$

$$2HP^u u^\varphi = [(R^2 E_r / h) + R^\varphi] / (1 - R_0/R) \quad (\text{B2.6})$$

$$2HM^v v^\varphi = [(R^2 E_r / h) - R^\varphi] / (1 - R_0/R) \quad (\text{B2.7})$$

$$\frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)(HM^v + HP^u) + (dR/d\varphi)(HM^v - HP^u)}{4HP^u HM^v (1 - R_0/R)} \quad (B2.8)$$

$$\frac{dr}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)(HM^v - HP^u) + (dR/d\varphi)(HM^v + HP^u)}{4HP^u HM^v (1 - R_0/R)} \quad (B2.9)$$

Relations (B2.1), (B2.2), (B2.3), (B2.4) are identical to the corresponding relations of the static metric. Consequently, the function $R(\varphi) = 1/w(\varphi)$ is strictly identical to the corresponding function of the static metric. Differences appear only in the calculation of the t, r coordinates, and in the calculation of the real time and distance intervals.

3 Ellipsoidal geodesics

Let us consider the case of a massive particle whose the $R(\varphi)$ function is approximately an ellipse which rotates around its vertical axis. Let us calculate the h and E_r values. We can set, from the equation (B2.3), for the R minimal value R_{\min} and for the R maximal value R_{\max} :

$$(dR/d\sigma)_{\min} = 0 \Rightarrow (1 - R_0 u_{\min}) [h^2(u_{\min})^2 + 1] = (E_r)^2 \quad (u_{\min} = 1/R_{\min})$$

$$(dR/d\sigma)_{\max} = 0 \Rightarrow (1 - R_0 u_{\max}) [h^2(u_{\max})^2 + 1] = (E_r)^2 \quad (u_{\max} = 1/R_{\max})$$

$$h^2(u_{\min})^2 - R_0 h^2(u_{\min})^3 - R_0 u_{\min} = h^2(u_{\max})^2 - R_0 h^2(u_{\max})^3 - R_0 u_{\max}$$

$$h^2(u_{\max} + u_{\min}) - R_0 h^2[(u_{\max})^2 + (u_{\min})^2 + u_{\max} u_{\min}] - R_0 = 0$$

Let us consider now the case of a circle of radius R : ($u_{\max} = u_{\min} = 1/R = \text{constant number}$); we obtain:

$$2 h^2/R - 3 R_0 h^2/R^2 - R_0 = 0 \Rightarrow h^2[1 - 3 R_0/(2R)] = R R_0/2 \Rightarrow h^2/R^2 = [R_0/(2R)]/[1 - 3 R_0/(2R)]$$

From equation (5.3), as the R function is constant: $(1 - R_0/R)(h^2/R^2 + 1) = (E_r)^2$

$$(E_r)^2 = (1 - R_0/R) \left[\frac{[R_0/(2R)]}{[1 - 3R_0/(2R)]} + 1 \right] = (1 - R_0/R)^2/[1 - 3R_0/(2R)]$$

$$\frac{h^2/R^2}{(E_r)^2} = \frac{[R_0/(2R)]/[1 - 3R_0/(2R)]}{(1 - R_0/R)^2/[1 - 3R_0/(2R)]} = \frac{[R_0/(2R)]}{(1 - R_0/R)^2} \Rightarrow \frac{R E_r/h}{(1 - R_0/R)} = \sqrt{\frac{2R}{R_0}} = \sqrt{\frac{R}{GM/c^2}} \Rightarrow \frac{R^2 E_r/h}{(1 - R_0/R)} = \frac{R\sqrt{R}}{\sqrt{GM/c^2}}$$

Let us set: V_r the radial velocity, V_T the orbital velocity.

$$\frac{dL_r}{c dT} = (V_r/c) = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)(HM^v - HP^u) + (dR/d\varphi)(HM^v + HP^u)}{(R^2 E_r/h)(HM^v + HP^u) + (dR/d\varphi)(HM^v - HP^u)}$$

$$(V_T)^2 = (R)^2 \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dT} \right)^2 = (R)^2 \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dt} \right)^2 \left(\frac{dt}{dT} \right)^2$$

$$(c dT)^2 = 4HM^v HP^u (1 - R_0/R) dt^2; \quad \frac{dt}{d\varphi} = \frac{(R^2 E_r/h)(HM^v + HP^u)}{(1 - R_0/R) 4HP^u HM^v} \Rightarrow (V_T)^2 = R^2 \frac{GM/c^2}{R^3} \frac{(4HP^u HM^v)^2}{(HM^v + HP^u)^2} \frac{c^2}{4HM^v HP^u (1 - R_0/R)}$$

$$(V_T)^2 = \frac{GM/R}{(1 - R_0/R)} \frac{4HP^u HM^v}{(HM^v + HP^u)^2} \quad (B3.1)$$

$$(V_r/c) = \frac{HM^v - HP^u}{HM^v + HP^u} \quad (B3.2)$$